

Thermal performance enhancement of organic phase change materials using spent diatomite from the palm oil bleaching process as support

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Abstract: In this study, PCMs supported in new, spent, and thermally treated diatomite were prepared, aiming for a renewable PCM for potential application in thermal energy storage in buildings. The PCMs were prepared by incorporating the organic phase (esters of palm oil and commercial stearic acid in different proportions) in diatomite (new, used and calcined). Subsequently, the PCMs with the highest latent heat of fusion and with a temperature range of phase change close to the thermal comfort were selected by differential scanning calorimetry (DSC) analyses. To establish the thermal and chemical stability of the PCMs, DSC, thermogravimetry (TGA), and Fourier-transform infrared spectroscopy (FT-IR) analyses were performed at 0, 120, 240 and 360 thermal cycles. Finally, it was determined that PCMs containing 100 % of commercial stearic acid esters and impregnated into new and calcined diatomite have long term thermal and chemical stability, so they are potential and renewable PCMs for energy saving.

Keywords: Fatty acid esters, diatomaceous earth, diatomite, phase change materials, renewable PCMs

1. INTRODUCTION

The energy demand required to maintain thermal comfort in buildings has grown continuously in the last years, due to an increasing number of users and consequently, a growing demand of air conditioning systems in the market [1,2]. The energy required for the operation of air conditioning systems, is mainly sourced from fossil fuels [3]. However, the use of fossil fuels for energy purposes represents a constant environmental concern, since its use is associated with the emission of greenhouse gases, which contribute to climate change and environmental pollution [4].

The use of renewable energy sources, such as thermal energy storage systems and PCMs, can reduce the energy consumption associated to the use of air conditioning systems in buildings [5]. The latent heat of a material can store 5 to 10 times more energy than its sensible heat [6,7]. During heating-cooling stages, PCMs undergo a physical transformation known as fusion-solidification cycle, which is completely reversible [8]. In the melting process, the material absorbs energy from the surroundings while remaining at a constant temperature. On the other hand, in the solidification process, the stored energy is delivered to the surroundings. This energy, which is absorbed and released at constant

temperature during the fusion-solidification cycle, can be used to reduce heating and cooling-associated energy demand in buildings while maintaining thermal comfort [9].

The use of PCMs in buildings requires materials that present phase change temperature ranges that correspond to the thermal comfort range (18-30 °C) [10], and with high values of fusion heat. In such conditions, a PCM improves the level of thermal comfort and reduces temperature fluctuations in buildings [4,11].

An important factor in determining the performance of a PCM is the analysis of its stability over time. For this purpose, temperature conditions are simulated to allow the material reaches both its melting point and its solidification point. After the application of these heating and cooling cycles, their chemical and thermal stability are evaluated [12]. The chemical and thermal stability of a PCM is evidenced when the chemical structure and thermal properties (latent heat of fusion and temperature range of phase change) of the material do not present changes after the application of thermal cycles. In addition, thermal stability also refers to the fact that the material does not decompose in the temperature range in which it is going to operate [13].

In recent years, various organic and inorganic materials have been studied as potential PCMs for application in buildings [7]. Commercially available PCMs for such applications include inorganic salts and non-biodegradable paraffins (hydrocarbons); however, their cost and availability on a large scale are major barriers for their use [9,14]. Organic PCMs have some advantages over inorganic ones, such as: non-toxicity, better thermal properties and long-term thermal reliability. Also, they present little degradation after the application of several heating-cooling cycles [15].

Paraffins are by far the most studied organic PCMs [7]. However, such PCMs do not come from renewable sources and their use requires a deeper understanding of their carbon footprint and associated environmental impact [13,16,17]. According to Rozanna et al. (2004), fatty acid esters are an environmental-friendly alternative to commercial PCMs. These materials have good chemical stability, are non-toxic, non-corrosive, renewably-sourced; furthermore, in their liquid state they have sufficient surface tension to be retained in support materials [18].

Xu et al. (2014) determined that methyl stearate and methyl palmitate mixtures have a great potential as PCMs for buildings. Both methyl stearate and methyl palmitate can be sourced renewably from palm oil. Indeed, palm oil composition includes 32 to 48 % of palmitic acid, 36 to 53% of oleic acid, 6 to 12% of linoleic acid, 3 to 6% stearic acid, among the main fatty acids [19,20].

Despite the potential applications of renewable organic materials as PCMs, their energy storage capacity is lower than that present in commercial hydrocarbon-based PCMs [6]. However, studies have been carried out on the effect of the addition of heterogeneous nucleating agents, such as silver, copper, carbon, titanium oxide, among others; in the thermal properties of PCMs [21,22,23]. The use of nucleation agents that induce a crystallization of the organic components is intended to increase heat transfer and improve the storage characteristics of PCMs [21,23].

In general, PCMs are encapsulated in porous materials, fibers and polymeric micro and macro capsules, to retain their liquid phase during the melting process [13]. The use of polymeric matrices for PCMs encapsulation generates free spaces during fusion-solidification processes that create heat transfer resistance [8,9]. In addition, several investigations have been reported in previous works on PCMs supported in porous materials [1,11,15,24,25,26]. These materials remain solid even when the melting point is reached at the phase change. According to Fleischer (2015), supported PCMs present higher specific heat and latent heat for the phase transition temperature region and higher thermal

conductivity, compared to the encapsulated PCMs. In addition, PCMs stabilized in porous supports do not require containers, and unlike encapsulated PCMs, the volume of the material does not change [25].

Additionally, Jeong et al. (2013) determined that the incorporation of PCMs in porous materials, using vacuum, allows to improve the thermal properties of the PCMs and achieve a better impregnation of the organic phase in the porous surface of the material. These advantages make these types of PCMs potential energy storage materials for use in buildings [1,11,24].

Diatomite or diatomaceous earth is an amorphous siliceous mineral with a variety of unique properties; including a structure of high porosity (80 - 90%), thermostability, low density, high purity, excellent absorption capacity, is chemically inert and relatively low cost [1]. These properties enable the use of diatomaceous earth as a support material for PCMs [25,27].

Currently, diatomite is mainly used in the discoloration or bleaching of edible oils due to its ability to absorb dissolved dyes, phosphatides, fatty acids, gums, traces of metals, etc. [28,29]. However, diatomaceous earths are used only once during vegetable oil bleaching, representing an industrial waste that is usually landfilled. For this reason, its final disposition implies both an economic cost and a potential source of soil pollution [29,30]. Among the different alternatives to the final disposition of spent diatomite, thermal or solvent regeneration, incineration, brick and block production and biodigestion are to be considered [29]. Regarding regeneration of spent diatomite, it can be achieved through thermal processes, extraction with solvents or a combination of both [29]. Thermal treatments for regenerating used or spent diatomaceous earth, temperatures above 600 ° C should be used to ensure organics removal [30].

It should be emphasized that no information is available on the use of diatomaceous earth from the oil bleaching process as a support material for the elaboration of phase change materials. In this sense, the present study aims to provide initial information on the development of phase change materials (PCMs) from palm oil extraction industry residues, which currently have no economic value.

2. MATERIAL AND METHODS

2.1 Materials

In the present work, PCMs composed of a support material and an organic phase were prepared and studied. As support material for the PCMs, new, spent (diatomaceous earth from the bleaching process of crude palm oil), and thermally treated spent diatomite were used. As the organic phase, mixtures of palm oil and commercial stearic acid esters were used in different proportions.

The crude palm oil and the spent diatomite that were used in the present investigation were obtained from an oil extraction company in Ecuador. In addition, commercial stearic acid was purchased locally.

2.2 Preparation of the PCMs

2.2.1 Characterization of palm oil and commercial stearic acid

The characterization of palm oil and commercial stearic acid consisted of the fatty acids quantification. For this purpose, gas chromatography analyzes were performed on a Perkin Elmer Clarus 500 chromatograph. Extra pure helium 5.0 was used as the carrier gas [32]. In addition, two analyzes were performed in rapid succession for each sample, until the obtained error was less than 5 % [33].

2.2.2 Preparation of palm oil and commercial stearic acid esters

For the preparation of esters of crude palm oil and commercial stearic acid, conventional trans esterification was carried out with methanol. For this purpose, sulfuric acid (H_2SO_4) was used as catalyst and 2 % w/w was added with respect to the mass of reactants. A fatty acid/methanol molar ratio of 1:10 was used. The process was carried out at 55.0 °C and for 5 h. For the purification, the product obtained was washed with water and then with ethyl ether [34].

2.2.3 Characterization of esters of palm oil and stearic acid

Esters of both palm oil and commercial stearic acid were characterized by gas chromatography and DSC. To determine qualitatively and quantitatively the composition of the esters used, gas chromatography analyzes were performed on a Perkin Elmer chromatograph. Sample preparation consisted of a 2 000 ppm dilution with petroleum ether and then passed through a Millipore Millex-HV 0.45 μm filter [35].

On the other hand, the esters were characterized by DSC in a Q 2000 1714, TA Instruments apparatus. The phase change temperature and latent heat of fusion were determined for each one of the obtained esters. Measurements were carried out at 0 to 60 °C with a heating rate of 4 °C/min under an inert atmosphere of nitrogen with a flow rate of 20 mL/min [13]. The phase change temperature range considered was from T onset to T end determined by the equipment.

2.2.4 Characterization of spent diatomite.

The spent diatomite was characterized by a proximal analysis that considered the determination of moisture, ash content, volatiles and fixed carbon in accordance with BS EN standards [39]. The moisture content was determined by gravimetry based on BS EN 18134-1 standard [37]. The determination of volatile matter and ash content was carried out based on BS EN 15148 and BS EN 18122, respectively [37,38].

Additionally, the oil content in the spent diatomite was determined through solvent extraction [28]. After the extraction was complete, the sample was dried at 110 °C for 4 hours. The amount of oil retained was determined by gravimetry.

2.2.5 Calcination of spent diatomaceous earth

The spent diatomite was calcined at 700 °C and 1 hour. Those conditions allow to a better use of spent diatomite because its pore contents can be eliminated [1].

2.2.6 Preparation of phase change materials (PCMs)

For the preparation of the PCMs, new, spent, and thermally treated diatomite were used as support material for mixtures of oil esters palm and commercial stearic acid as the organic phase.

2.2.6.1 Experimental design

In order to determine the PCMs that have the most suitable thermal properties to store thermal energy in buildings, a completely randomized experimental design (DCA) was proposed for each type of support material. The factor studied was the ester proportion of palm oil and commercial stearic acid esters in five levels (100 - 0, 75 - 25, 50 - 50, 25 - 75, 0 - 100%) (w/w), respectively.

2.2.6.2 Impregnation of the esters of palm oil and stearic acid in the support materials

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In order to obtain the PCMs, the vacuum impregnation method was applied by placing 10 g of the support material inside a kitasato flask, which was connected to a water trap and a vacuum pump, as indicated in Figure 1; a vacuum pressure of 27 kPa was maintained for 30 minutes. The organic phase entered into the flask, and the same vacuum pressure was maintained for 90 minutes [1,17].

Figure 1. Schematic representation of the vacuum impregnation process

In order to determine the energy storage capacity of each prepared PCM, the latent heat of fusion was quantified in each case. For this, differential DSC scanning calorimetry analyzes were done in triplicate, under the same conditions as those mentioned in section 2.2.3.

By using Statgraphics Centurion XVI statistical software, the PCM that had the highest latent heat of fusion and a phase change temperature range close to the temperature range of thermal comfort (18 - 30) ° C were selected from each type of support material [10].

Once the materials with the characteristics described above were selected, their thermal and chemical stability was evaluated by the application of heating and cooling cycles.

2.3 Evaluation of the thermal cycle's effect

To establish the thermal and chemical stability of the selected heating and cooling cycles (120, 240 and 360 cycles) were applied. For this, the phase change materials selected in section 2.2.6 were heated to the phase change temperature; for later, to cool them until reaching its solidification temperature. For the heating of the PCMs, a stove was used which was maintained at 50 °C. On the other hand, for the cooling process, a refrigerator was used which was maintained at about 8 °C. These temperatures were selected to ensure both melting and solidification temperatures were reached [12].

Thermal stability of the PCMs was analyzed by DSC under the same conditions detailed in section 2.2.3 and by TGA in a Shimadzu equipment in a temperature range of 25 to 600 °C, with a heating rate of 10 °C/min and a nitrogen flow of 50 mL/min were carried out [1]. Moreover, chemical stability was analyzed by an infrared spectrophotometer with Fourier transform Perkin Elmer, Frontier in a wavelength range of 4000-400 cm^{-1} . The spectra of PCMs without exposure and exposure to different cycles were compared to identify chemical changes in the material produced by the effect of thermal degradation [1].

Additionally, to evaluate the morphology of the PCMs and the possible changes after the application of 120 thermal cycles, scanning electron microscopy (SEM) analyzes were performed in a TESCAN Vega 3 microscope with a voltage of 20 kV [40].

By comparing the analyzes described above, the most suitable PCMs for temperature regulation in buildings were determined according to their thermal and chemical stability; in other words, those that did not show changes after the application of heating and cooling cycles [8].

3. Results and discussion

3.1 Properties of the palm oil and stearic acid esters, and spent diatomaceous earth

The results of the fatty acid composition in palm oil and commercial stearic acid are presented in Table 1. As can be seen, trans-9 elaidic acid (trans configuration of oleic acid), palmitic acid and linoleic acid are the most abundant acids present in palm oil (95.82 %). These results correspond to those presented by Melero et al. (2010).

Tabla 1. Composición de ácidos grasos presentes en el aceite crudo de palma y en el ácido esteárico comercial y composición de metil ésteres presentes en el aceite crudo de palma y en el ácido esteárico comercial esterificados

Fatty acids/ methyl ester	Palm oil	Comercial stearic acid	Palm oil ester	Comercial stearic acid ester
Trans-9 Eláidico	43,61	0,00	50,17	0,00
Palmitic	36,78	48,18	20,03	49,20
Linoleic	15,43	0,00	15,80	0,00
Stearic	4,13	51,10	13,72	50,80
Caprilic	0,05	0,00	0,28	0,00
Miristic	0,00	0,72	0,00	0,00
Total	100,00	100,00	100,00	100,00

In addition, it can be observed that commercial stearic acid presents only 51.10% of pure stearic acid, this could be because the purification process of stearic acid requires substances such as acetone, acetonitrile and ethanol, which make the product more expensive [41]. Although commercial stearic acid did not exhibit high purity, its economic value is less than pure stearic acid; which would make it possible to obtain lower cost PCMs. Moreover, Table 1 shows the composition of methyl esters present in palm oil and commercial stearic acid after the esterification process. These results allowed to know the composition of the mixtures that were used as organic phase in the preparation of the PCMs.

In Figure 2, the DSC melting curves of the palm oil and commercial stearic acid esters are presented. It was found that the phase change temperature range corresponds to 0.6 - 43.0 °C and 16.4 - 35.7 °C; and latent heat of fusion values of 13.86 J/g and 86.42 J/g, respectively. The value of the latent heat of fusion of palm oil esters was lower than that of commercial stearic acid esters. This behavior may be because the temperature range study did not include values such as the melting temperature of the trans-9 methyl elaidate (isomer of the methyl oleate) present in palm oil esters (-36 °C) [34]. This temperature was not considered because the temperature range of interest corresponded to values close to the thermal comfort temperature range.

Diatomaceous earth, used in the process of bleaching palm oil, has a moisture level of 3.26 %; 55.68 % ashes; 0.49 % of fixed carbon and 40.67 % of volatiles (26.16 % of oil retained in its pores and 14.51 % of impurities acquired in the process). According to O'Brien (2009), these impurities correspond to phospholipids, carotenoids and trace metals.

In order to use the spent diatomaceous earth as a support material for PCMs, it was necessary to eliminate the moisture content and volatile matter in such a way as to avoid the decrease of the surface available to be occupied by the organic phase in the preparation of the PCMs [1,30].

Figure 2. DSC melting curves of the methyl ester of palm oil and the commercial stearic acid methyl ester

3.2 Preparation of phase change materials

In addition, the nonlinear trend observed in Figure 4, both in the spent diatomaceous earth and in the calcined, could be attributed to the fact that in the pores the same amount of esters was not retained as in the new diatomaceous earth due to the presence of palm oil, impurities and the decrease of the porous surface as a result of the heat treatment applied [1,28]. Therefore, the amount of energy that PCMs can store depends on the amount of esters retained in the porous structures of the carrier materials, as well as the impurities they could present [44].

Figure 4. Fisher's mean difference (LSD) for PCMs impregnated into new, spent and thermally treated diatomaceous earth.

Table 2 shows that the phase change temperature range is higher in palm oil esters than in commercial stearic acid esters, these results could be due to esterified palm oil is composed of different esters of fatty acids whose melting points range from -36 °C to 39 °C [34]. In addition, it is noted that the

phase change temperature range decreases when the content of commercial stearic acid esters increases, this behavior could be explained since in the ester mixtures while increasing the proportion of commercial stearic acid esters the content of methyl palmitate and methyl stearate is higher than the other esters and their phase change temperatures are 31 °C and 39 °C, respectively [13].

Table 2. Temperature range of phase change and latent heat of fusion of the elaborated PCMs

Support material	Esters de P.O- esters de C.S.A composition (%-%)	T onset (°C)	T end (°C)	Latent heat of fusion (J/g)
New diatomaceous earth	100-0	0,9 ± 0,3	35,0 ± 1,3	11,78 ± 0,40
	75-25	10,8 ± 0,2	17,9 ± 1,5	27,87 ± 0,65
	50-50	2,2 ± 0,2	24,1 ± 1,5	41,86 ± 2,89
	25-75	19,2 ± 1,0	30,9 ± 0,7	56,52 ± 2,57
	0-100	17,5 ± 0,1	34,7 ± 1,1	66,27 ± 3,20
Spent diatomaceous earth	100-0	3,4 ± 0,4	26,3 ± 0,5	22,82 ± 0,04
	75-25	1,0 ± 0,7	42,5 ± 2,1	12,28 ± 0,19
	50-50	9,4 ± 0,7	41,3 ± 1,4	14,26 ± 0,33
	25-75	2,3 ± 0,6	25,0 ± 0,5	14,72 ± 0,40
	0-100	10,4 ± 0,1	25,7 ± 0,9	19,34 ± 0,20
Calcined diatomaceous earth	100-0	0,3 ± 0,1	36,2 ± 2,1	13,71 ± 0,21
	75-25	12,3 ± 0,7	26,3 ± 0,9	23,21 ± 2,88
	50-50	2,2 ± 0,3	21,3 ± 0,3	21,26 ± 0,35
	25-75	2,2 ± 0,4	16,9 ± 2,43	14,01 ± 0,46
	0-100	16,4 ± 0,4	33,5 ± 0,56	34,67 ± 2,56

P.O palm oil
C.S.A comercial stearic acid

On the other hand, the latent heat of fusion is higher when 100% methyl esters of commercial stearic acid are used for PCMs supported on new and calcined diatomaceous earth and when 100% methyl esters of oil of palm for PCMs supported on spent earths. However, as can be seen in Table 2, the phase change temperature range for the last one does not coincide with the thermal comfort range. Therefore, its use would not be the most suitable in buildings, because when using PCMs with a range of temperatures of greater phase change and that does not adjust to that of thermal comfort could decrease the capacity to store energy of the material [9,13]. Additionally, the PCMs, whose organic phase corresponds to 100% esters of commercial stearic acid, were selected, whose composition (determined by chromatography) is 49.20% of methyl palmitate and 50.80% of methyl stearate, supported in each of the materials evaluated (new, spent and calcined diatomaceous earth).

3.3 Evaluation of the effect of thermal cycles

To determine the applicability of PCMs (100% commercial stearic acid), selected in section 3.2, as thermal energy storage systems, heating and cooling cycles were applied, and thermal stability was analyzed by DSC and TGA analyses and the chemical stability by FT-IR analyses [12].

The DSC melting curves of PCMs impregnated on new, spent and calcined diatomaceous earth are presented in Figure 5.A, 5.B and 5.C, respectively. In all cases, after 360 thermal cycles, an increase in the area of the curve representing the magnitude of the latent heat of fusion is evidenced [7]. This behavior could be explained by the fact that during the application of the thermal cycles the temperature conditions facilitating the crystallization process of the esters were favored. This process could produce an increase in the latent heat of fusion of the evaluated PCMs [46]. This increase could allow the material to absorb a greater amount of energy in a smaller mass of the same, facilitating the establishment of thermal comfort conditions in buildings [8]. For PCMs impregnated in calcined diatomaceous earth, the increase in latent heat after the application of the 360 thermal cycles is

54.80% with respect to the initial value, as compared to the 10.19% and 35.73% that is evidenced in PCMs impregnated in new and used diatomaceous earth, respectively. As shown in Figure 5.B, 360 cycles are required to increase the latent heat of fusion in the PCMs supported on diatomaceous earth used; however, in the PCMs supported on new and calcined diatomaceous earth this increase was visible after the application of 120 cycles. This behavior could be attributed to the presence of fatty acids retained in the pores of the residual diatomaceous earth, since their thermal behavior differs from that of esters [18]. On the other hand, the variation in the melting temperature ranges are minimal for the three cases since the curves do not present horizontal displacement. However, to establish the cause of the increase in the latent heat of fusion, the changes in the chemical structures of the PCMs were analyzed by FT-IR [13]. The results of these analyzes are presented in Figure 7 and 8.

— 0 cycles — 120 cycles — 240 cycles — 360 cycles

Figure 5. DSC melting curves of PCMs supported in (a) new, (b) spent, (c) calcined, diatomite before and after the application of 0, 120, 240 and 360 thermal cycles, using 100% commercial stearic acid esters.

On the other hand, by the thermogravimetric analyzes, it was determined that the PCMs do not present degradation at low temperatures as can be seen in Figure 6.A, 6.B and 6.C; since the loss of mass, when the PCMs were exposed to a heating from room temperature to a temperature of approximately 100 °C, is less than 2%. According to Rathod and Banerjee (2013), this weight loss could be due to the loss of moisture present in the PCMs. However, as shown in Figure 6.B, after the application of 360 thermal cycles, the decomposition temperature of the PCM supported on spent diatomite decreases, this could be due to the fact that after the application of the thermal cycles, the decomposition of the components of the palm oil present in its pores was produced as indicated by Wan Nik et al. (2005). This change in the thermal decomposition resistance corresponds to what is established in Figure 5.B, since a change in both the phase change temperature range and the latent heat of fusion value after the application of 360 cycles is evidenced.

— 0 cycles — 120 cycles — 240 cycles — 360 cycles

Figure 6. Thermograms of PCMs supported in (a) new, (b) spent, (c) calcined, diatomite before and after the application of 0, 120, 240 and 360 thermal cycles, using 100% commercial stearic acid esters.

In Figure 6.A it is not evident that the resistance to thermal degradation improved in the PCMs supported in new diatomaceous earth after the application of the thermal cycles. On the other hand, Figure 6.C shows that the PCM supported in calcined diatomaceous earth is degraded to higher temperatures after the application of 360 thermal cycles, that is to say it presents an improvement in its resistance to the thermal degradation. This result is corroborated by the improvement of the thermal properties observed in Figure 5.C and could be attributed to the rearrangement of the esters molecules and thus to the formation of crystalline zones [46].

For the three cases evaluated by TGA it was evidenced that the organic phase do not released of the porous material; since at 100 °C which is a temperature higher than the phase change temperature of the PCMs there is no loss of the organic phase [1]. This indicates that the analyzed PCMs are thermally stable and can be used as energy storage systems [15].

The FT-IR analyzes were performed before and after the application of 120, 240 and 360 thermal cycles, in order to identify changes in the chemical structure of the PCMs due to the thermal cycles. In Figure 7, the presence of $-\text{CH}_2$, $-\text{CH}_3$ groups and C-O, C=O bonds of the esters of commercial stearic acid are observed, since by gas chromatography it was determined that it consists of methyl stearate ($\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2$) and methyl palmitate ($\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{34}\text{O}_2$). Peaks at 720 and 1 468 cm^{-1} were found which correspond to the symmetric and asymmetric vibration of the $-\text{CH}_3$ group, respectively. In addition, the symmetric and asymmetric vibration of the $-\text{CH}_2$ group is evident in the peaks present at 2 850 and 2 917 cm^{-1} . The stretching vibration of the C=O group is evidenced at 1 740 cm^{-1} and the asymmetric vibration of C-O-C at 1 170 cm^{-1} [1].

Figure 7. FT-IR spectrum of the organic phase and support materials used to make the PCMs

On the other hand, the new, spent and calcined diatomaceous earth share peaks at 1 635 cm^{-1} and 470 - 477 cm^{-1} corresponding to the vibration of the O-H group and the vibration of the Si-O group, respectively. In the new diatomaceous earth, a peak at 792 cm^{-1} attributed to the O-H group is

observed, the Si-O-Si vibration at $1\,093\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and at $3\,417\text{ cm}^{-1}$ the presence of the Si-OH group [8]. The spent and calcined diatomaceous earth share the following peaks at $539 - 540\text{ cm}^{-1}$, $1\,545\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $3\,417\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the vibration of the O-P-O, Si-O-Si and Si-OH, respectively [1,48]. The spent diatomaceous earth has peaks at $1\,740\text{ cm}^{-1}$ and $2\,920\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to the stretching vibration of the C=O group and the asymmetric vibration of the $-\text{CH}_2$ group. The presence of this last peak is due to the fact that as mentioned in section 3.1 the diatomaceous earth contains 26.16 % of residual palm oil in its pores and the calcined diatomaceous earth does not present these peaks because the organic compound of the palm oil decomposes at temperatures above $380\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ [13,47]. On the other hand, the calcined diatomaceous earth has a peak at $3\,748\text{ cm}^{-1}$ corresponding to Si-OH and at 944 cm^{-1} the Si-O silanol stretching vibration [8]. Therefore it is observed that the three support materials have the proper bonds of a siliceous material such as diatomaceous earth [1].

In Figures 8.A and 8.B, it is observed that the peaks of both new and calcined diatomaceous earth and the ester are maintained after the impregnation process. However, for the PCMs supported on diatomaceous earth used, there are displacements of the peaks after the impregnation process. Particularly, from 539 cm^{-1} to 525 cm^{-1} and from 1045 cm^{-1} to 1095 cm^{-1} ; the cause of these displacements could be attributed to the presence of crude palm oil, retained in the pores of the diatomaceous earth, which produces interactions with both the support material and the organic phase of the PCM [43]. Therefore, it was determined that there is no chemical interaction between the support material and the organic phase, by impregnating the esters on the new and calcined diatomaceous earth [1].

Figure 8. A) FT-IR spectra of the PCM/new diatomite, B) FT-IR spectra of the PCM / spent diatomite, (C) FT-IR spectra of the PCM/ calcined diatomite before and after the application of 0, 120, 240 and 360 thermal cycles using 100% commercial stearic acid esters.

Additionally, it is observed that both the PCMs constituted by new diatomaceous earth and by calcined diatomaceous earth present chemical stability, since the peaks that present the spectrograms, before and after the application of the thermal cycles, coincide. The presence of a peak at 792 cm^{-1} attributed to the O-H group and the displacement of 1045 to 1096 cm^{-1} , which for both cases correspond to the vibration of the Si-O-Si bond [8]. However, these peaks correspond to bonds present in the new and calcined diatomaceous earth, so that the chemical stability of the PCMs supported on spent diatomaceous earth is not affected by the application of the thermal cycles.

The changes in the microstructure of the PCMs were analyzed before and after the application of 120 thermal cycles, since after the application of the same the increase of the latent heat of fusion was greater for both the PCMs supported in new and calcined diatomaceous earth as was shown in Figure 5. In Figures 9.D, 9.E and 9.F, it is evident that the PCMs present an ordering of the esters on the support material after the application of the thermal cycles. This behavior would be explained by the fact that, during the heating and cooling of the PCMs, the temperature conditions leading to the formation of crystalline zones were propitiated. Because the fatty acid esters are polymers and most polymers go through a heterogeneous nucleation (crystallization) process when the temperature is raised to the melting temperature and then the crystallization temperature by cooling. Then, this rearrangement is produced by the increase in the formation of nucleated spherulites resulting in an increase in the latent heat of fusion [46,49].

However, for the PCMs impregnated in calcined diatomaceous earth, after the 120 thermal cycles, the degree of ordering of the ester molecules is greater, since the formation of rounded lamellas that are established one on the other is observed. It should be emphasized that the heterogeneous nucleation process is favored when other materials (inorganic components, catalysts and even other polymers) are added to the polymers [46]. Then, to determine the agent that acted on these lands, FT-IR analyzes presented in Figure 7 and SEM analyses presented in Table 3 were used. In the spectrograms, a higher area peak in the calcined diatomaceous earth is observed than in the spent earth, at 540 cm^{-1} and 539 cm^{-1} , respectively, and which is not evident in the new diatomaceous earth. According to Jastrzbski et al. (2011), the bands of the FT-IR of $500 - 670\text{ cm}^{-1}$ correspond to the vibration of the O-P-O bonds. Chemical analysis confirmed the presence of phosphorus in 0.55 % in

the spent diatomaceous earth and in 1.21 % in the calcined diatomaceous earth, and the new diatomaceous earth do not present this element.

Figure 9. Summary of scanning electron microscopy results. Microstructure of the PCM supported in (A) new, (B) spent, and (C) calcined, diatomite before the application of thermal cycling at 4,000 increases using 100% commercial stearic acid esters. Microstructure of the PCM supported in (D) new, (E) spent, and (F) calcined, diatomite after the application of 120 thermal cycling at 4,000 increases using 100% commercial stearic acid esters.

Table 3. Chemical analysis of new, used and calcined diatomaceous earth

Element	New diatomaceous earth		Used diatomaceous earth		Calcined diatomaceous earth	
	Percentage (%)	Error (%)	Percentage (%)	Error (%)	Percentage (%)	Error (%)
Carbon	26.99	12.77	43.73	22.39	10.61	7.08
Oxygen	51.49	17.98	41.14	20.00	54.77	18.96
Magnesium	0.03	0.09	1.04	0.32	1.86	0.39
Aluminum	0.57	0.18	2.31	0.46	5.26	0.77
Silicon	19.36	2.11	9.29	1.27	21.22	2.42
Phosphorus	-	-	0.55	0.18	1.21	0.24
Sulfur	-	-	0.22	0.13	0.69	0.17
Potassium	-	-	-	-	0.16	0.11
Calcium	0.59	0.15	0.65	0.17	2.16	0.27
Titanium	-	-	-	-	0.03	0.09
Iron	0.20	0.12	1.05	0.22	1.88	0.24
Copper	-	-	-	-	0.14	0.11
Sodium	0.78	0.27	-	-	-	-

Then, as Loh et al. (2013) shown, carotenoids and phosphatides are retained in palm oil bleaching earth after their use. Specifically, in the study carried out by Silva et al. (2013), it was found that crude palm oil has a phosphorus content of $(19.1 \pm 0.02 \text{ mg / kg})$ and $(454.0 \pm 5.5 \text{ mg / kg})$ carotenoids remaining in the diatomaceous earth during the bleaching process. Total phosphorus content is a total measure of phosphatides as both phospholipids and gums [50,51].

Therefore, it was determined that the agent, which probably facilitates the crystallization of the esters, corresponds to the inorganic part of the phosphatides present in the spent diatomaceous earth from the crude palm oil bleaching process. This is verified by the results of the FT-IR analyzes which indicated the presence of O-P-O bonds in both the spent and calcined diatomaceous earth. However, in the calcined diatomaceous earth a higher concentration of these bonds was evidenced than in the spent diatomaceous earth. This can be explained by the fact that, when high temperatures are applied, most organic compounds are volatilized, including carotenoids, resulting in increased concentration of the O-P-O bonds in calcined earth [29].

Based on the results obtained, it was found that the residual diatomaceous earth could be used as support materials for PCMs, if they are calcined; since this process facilitates the action of the nucleation and crystallization agents that allow to improve the thermal properties of the PCMs; specifically, increasing the latent heat of fusion and the resistance to thermal degradation as the heating-cooling cycles pass, and the drawbacks of the use of spent diatomaceous earth without heat treatment, such as detachment of the organic phase during the application of thermal cycles and the reduction of its thermal degradation resistance are deleted.

CONCLUSIONS

The present study has been able to determine that the diatomaceous earth, residue of the bleaching process of palm oil, calcined is a potential support material for the development of PCMs, its use allows the increase of the latent heat of fusion in 54.80 % and increased resistance to thermal degradation.

According to the statistical analysis, the best conditions of calcination temperature and time of the residual diatomaceous earth were 700 °C and 1 h, with a percentage of impregnation of 71.83%.

PCMs impregnated with 100% commercial stearic acid methyl esters supported on new and calcined diatomaceous earth presented higher energy storage capacity in the comfort temperature range with latent heat of melting values of $66.27 \pm 3, 20 \text{ J/g}$, $17.5 - 34.7 \text{ °C}$ and $34.67 \pm 2.56 \text{ J/g}$, $16.4 - 33.5 \text{ °C}$, respectively.

The application of thermal cycles determined the long-term thermal and chemical stability of the materials supported in new and calcined diatomaceous earth. In such a way that they can be applied as systems of storage of thermal energy in buildings.

The phosphorus present in the residual diatomaceous earth allowed the increase of the latent heat of fusion by 54.80 % and improved the resistance of the PCMs to the thermal degradation acting as a nucleating agent (crystallization).

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